

OPEN LETTER

Continuous Auditing and Continuous Certification in MEDINA – Security Auditor’s View [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

Tatu Suhonen¹, Cristina Martínez ²¹Nixu Certification Ltd, ESPOO, 02150, Finland²Fundacion Tecnalía Research & Innovation, San Sebastián, Basque Country, E-20009, Spain

V1 First published: 23 Nov 2023, 3:208
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16703.1>
 Latest published: 01 May 2024, 3:208
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16703.2>

Abstract

This paper discusses views on continuous auditing and continuous certification in the context of the MEDINA EU project and the security auditing industry. Based on an introduction of MEDINA, the notions of continuous auditing and continuous certification are introduced from a security auditor’s perspective to discuss the opportunities and challenges related to these topics. The paper also discusses further actions beyond this project in order to provide feedback on how continuous auditing and certification can be developed and introduced to the market.

Keywords

EUCS, Continuous Auditing, Continuous Certification

This article is included in the [Cloud-based Technologies](#) collection.

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2
version 2 (revision) 01 May 2024		
version 1 23 Nov 2023	 view	

1. **Henrique Santos** , Universidade do Minho, Braga, Portugal

2. **Johan David Michels** , Queen Mary University of London, London, UK

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Corresponding authors: Tatu Suhonen (tatu.suhonen@nixu.com), Cristina Martínez (crisrina.martinez@tecnalia.com)

Author roles: **Suhonen T:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **Martínez C:** Conceptualization, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952633 (Security framework to achieve a continuous audit-based certification in compliance with the EU-wide cloud security certification scheme [MEDINA]). This work has been partially funded by the European project MEDINA (Horizon 2020 Research and innovation Programme, under the grant agreement no 952633).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2023 Suhonen T and Martínez C. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Suhonen T and Martínez C. **Continuous Auditing and Continuous Certification in MEDINA – Security Auditor's View [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2023, 3:208 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16703.1>

First published: 23 Nov 2023, 3:208 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16703.1>

Disclaimer

The views expressed in this article are those of the authors. Publication in Open Research Europe does not imply endorsement of the European Commission.

Introduction

One of the recognized reasons for the still limited adoption of Cloud Computing in the EU is the customers' perceived lack of security and transparency in this technology^{1,2}. Cloud Service Providers (CSPs) usually rely on security certifications as a means to improve transparency and trustworthiness. However, European CSPs still face multiple challenges for certifying their services (e.g., fragmentation in the certification market, and lack of mutual recognition of certification schemes adding workload related to maintaining certificates). In this context, the EU Cybersecurity Act (EU CSA, approved in June 2019³) proposes improving customers' trust in the European ICT market through a set of EU-wide certification schemes. One of those schemes, the European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Service (EUCS)⁴ is being developed by the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA). For a selected set of high-level assurance requirements, the EUCS proposes the following notion of continuous (automated) monitoring: the requirements related to continuous monitoring typically mention "automated monitoring" or "automatically monitor" in their text. The intended meaning of "monitor automatically" is:

1. Gather data to analyse some aspects of the activity being monitored at discrete intervals at a sufficient frequency.
2. Compare the gathered data to a reference or otherwise determine conformity to specified requirements in the EUCS scheme.
3. Report deviations to subject matter experts who can analyse the deviations in a timely manner.
4. If the deviation indicates a nonconformity, then initiate a process for fixing the nonconformity.
5. If the non-conformity is major, notify the Conformance Assessment Body (CAB) of the issue, analysis, and planned resolution.

These requirements stop short of requiring any notion of continuous auditing, because technologies have not reached an adequate level of maturity. Nevertheless, the introduction of continuous auditing, at least for high-level assurance requirements, remains a mid- or long-term objective, and the introduction of automated monitoring requirements in at least some areas is a first step in that direction, which can be met with the technology available today. The EUCS notion of continuous monitoring conveys important technological and organizational challenges for stakeholders, which need to be carefully analysed and understood by all relevant stakeholders in order to benefit the adoption of this new certification scheme.

This paper focuses on discussing the notion of continuous auditing and continuous certification from the perspective of

an auditor. The observations and future recommendations are based on the innovations of the MEDINA project⁵ and the expertise of a Conformance Assessment Body (Nixu) working as one of the partners in the project as subject matter experts.

MEDINA framework

This section provides a simplified and brief overview of the MEDINA framework. For a broader understanding of the MEDINA framework and its components, it is recommended to read the paper "An architecture proposal for the MEDINA framework"⁶.

MEDINA is based on four main pillars that make the project relevant to the notion of continuous and automated monitoring for the security certification of cloud services:

1. **Metrics repository:** The EUCS provides a set of security requirements that shall be leveraged to certify cloud services. The lack of defined "compliance metrics" for assessing EUCS requirements could be a problem for Cloud Service Providers (CSP) and Conformance Assessment Bodies (CAB), which may have to leverage their own customised metrics for automatic application/assessment. To address this, the MEDINA framework includes a Catalogue of controls and metrics associated with the EUCS requirements, covering security topics such as information security organization, asset management, operational security, incident management and business continuity⁷.
2. **Risk-based approach for security controls:** The MEDINA framework includes a risk-based methodology that relies on a tool for the analysis of EUCS requirements, ensuring that compliance with these requirements is actually relevant for the CSP, depending on the its risk appetite. The tool evaluates the non-conformities and determines whether a non-conformity is major -leading to revocation of the certificate-, or the deviation is minor -and therefore the certificate should be maintained⁸.
3. **Certification language:** EUCS requirements are defined in natural language, so it is necessary to "translate" them into a machine-readable representation that facilitates the extraction of metrics. To this end, the MEDINA framework includes tools that make use of NLP (Natural Language Processing) techniques to recommend metrics for the evaluation of a given requirement, as well as for the extraction of the values of organisational metrics within normative documents⁹.
4. **Evidence collection and continuous audit:** In order to achieve continuous audit-based certification of cloud services, it is necessary to collect real technical evidence related to automated monitoring. To this end, the MEDINA framework includes tools and methodologies that manage the collection of evidence at both code and service level, thus supporting CSPs to apply for a high-assurance EUCS certificate. Digital evidence are continuously monitored and evaluated by MEDINA, and Blockchain

techniques are used to implement accountable monitoring¹⁰.

Figure 1 shows the high-level workflow of the MEDINA framework. Users of the solution, i.e. control owners, compliance managers and external auditors, have their own swimming line in the workflow and time flows from left to right. The components involved in each phase of the workflow are covered in more detail in 6. In addition, MEDINA deliverables¹ cover in detail each component and each phase of the framework processes. This paper focuses on those phases where the auditor is involved, i.e. the boxes marked in red in Figure 1.

MEDINA for auditors

In this section we discuss the effects of MEDINA to information security auditing. The analysis includes discussing changes to audit processes and audit methods in MEDINA, not forgetting the higher-level strategic discussion related to a change in the whole auditing industry.

From point-in-time audits to continuous auditing

MEDINA is offering a solution to one of the challenges in the current audit practice, which is the uncertainty of conformity between audits due to a lack of auditor presence in the auditee’s environment between audits¹¹. Why is this a problem? When an auditee suffers a breach or deliberately (or by accident)

acts against the rules of certification, it causes a reputation and brand impact to the CAB. Of course, it is the CAB’s interest to do their job with utmost professionalism, but anything can happen in-between audits. Perhaps a key employee of the auditee resigns, and security gradually starts to fail.

Most certification schemes follow an approach in which an onsite audit must be completed successfully before a certificate is granted. The certificate has a validity period, for example three years after which it must be renewed with another thorough audit, a recertification audit. Currently, to tackle the uncertainty with the auditee conforming to the requirements during the certificate’s validity period, some certification schemes, if not requiring an annual re-audit, require mandatory smaller scale surveillance audits, typically annually. Surveillance audits aim to ensure that any changes in the certification scope can be assessed and most importantly ensure that the auditee’s processes and actions still meet the criteria of certification. For example, the standard ISO/IEC 17021-1¹², which is applied to CABs providing ISO/IEC 27001 audits, enforces the surveillance audits in order to maintain confidence that the auditee still fulfils the requirements after the initial audit.

The challenge in this approach has always been that the audit is always a representation of the auditee’s current state during one point in time, and therefore the name *point-in-time audit*. There are limited ways to ensure that the auditee is at least maintaining the same level of security between audits, most importantly after the initial audit has been finished and

¹ <https://medina-project.eu/public-deliverables/>

Figure 1. High-level MEDINA workflow.

the certificate has been granted. In some cases, the auditee may consider the certification audit more as an annual project rather than as a continuous and integral part of daily work and is thus focusing majority of their efforts just prior to the audits. Certification (and security in general) is not a sprint; it is a continuous process. Ultimately an organisation should aim to be proactive instead of reactive and this is where continuous auditing may help. The relatively long period of inactivity between certification activities creates a certain trust factor in play. The auditor cannot always be present at the auditee and thus the opportunities to review the conformity status of an auditee is almost only limited to the surveillance audits, or if a complaint is filed against a certificate by a third party. Furthermore, the auditor can never achieve a 100% certainty in the audit results as audits are usually based on sampling.

By introducing continuous auditing, the uncertainty of compliance status between onsite audits can be lowered. Continuous auditing is achieved with MEDINA framework components by mapping the requirements to measurable metrics which in turn can be used to collect and assess evidence¹³. This evidence can be then evaluated by the auditor in each onsite audit throughout the audit cycle. A simplified illustration of the certification cycle is presented in [Figure 2](#).

Continuous auditing offers great opportunities both the auditee and the auditor. While the auditee can increase their general security awareness and enhance their security posture by implementing continuous monitoring and auditing capabilities and eventually increase customer trust, the auditor gets more assurance of the auditee's compliance throughout the certification cycle and has more extensive audit methods in use by utilizing automated tools to assist in gathering and storing evidence. For example, when doing an onsite audit, the auditor has only a limited time to analyse and audit a sample of cloud resources, even with the help of tools.

With continuous auditing the sample size can be extended significantly, and focus can be put on finding and analysing any anomalies in the audit results since the evaluation has been

done automatically for the auditor throughout the audit period. By extending the continuous auditing to continuous certification, the auditor can even further extend the usability of MEDINA by integrating the certificate life cycle management on top of continuous auditing¹⁴. This allows the auditor to get notified of non-conformities, and react to them accordingly, for example, by updating the certificate status to suspended in case of a nonconformity. Continuous certification is studied in more detail later in this paper.

It is important to notice that the implementation of automated tools does not necessarily reduce the workload of an auditor in an audit. Instead, it offers more ways to verify findings in more complex and larger environments. If we look at the current trends in information technology, it is evident that cloud-based solutions have become the go-to solution for many organizations. Assessing these environments can be challenging, any automated tools to help gather and analyse vast amounts of information are welcomed.

Additionally, a CAB can extend its service offering with continuous auditing services and improve audit effectiveness by implementing new innovations and technologies to the continuous auditing process. In the context of EUCS and MEDINA, a CAB could offer the following:

- EUCS and MEDINA certification training:
 - General, publicly available training aiming to aid understanding the concepts of EUCS, MEDINA and associated certification process.
- Certification audits for assurance level Substantial:
 - Certification audits according to EUCS specification.
- Certification audits for assurance level High with MEDINA:
 - Certification audits with continuous auditing services utilizing MEDINA.
 - Different MEDINA components used by the auditor.

Figure 2. Simplified certification life-cycle.

MEDINA and EUCS will provide significant business opportunities in the future. The demand for better assurance in cloud environments is already there, and MEDINA helps to provide supply to that demand.

Changes in audit methods and audit process

The addition of continuous auditing naturally means that the audit process is changed. The traditional approach to auditing, simplified drastically, is to review documentation, interview suitable persons and verify findings by conducting additional tests, such as process observations, sample reviews or technical tests. By utilizing continuous auditing, the last step, verification of results, can be done based on the results collected by automated tools.

The undeniable truth is that continuous auditing will benefit the auditor massively by doing much of the work for the auditor. The change is similar to what industrialization did to manufacturing: human touch is lost in the grass-root level of the process but is better utilized in a more productive role. Continuous auditing itself does not mean that the role of a CAB would be to just check measurement results and grant a certificate, but rather oversee that the whole automation process is implemented and functioning as intended in each auditee environment. Therefore, in an EUCS audit as part of the initial audit covered in section “From point-in-time audits to Continuous Auditing” the CAB will have to do a traditional (manual) assessment of the current situation based on the selected EUCS assurance level, and in level high the CAB has to evaluate the implementation of continuous monitoring components and confirm that the measurement results cover the scope of the audit and provide truthful results. Practically speaking, this would add a step to the audit to validate the configuration of the continuous monitoring tool implementation. However, this added time will be gained later when the evidence is assessed automatically.

Automated evidence gathering allows larger samples over longer periods of time to be used in an audit. On the other hand, some manual work is still required but with a standardized design of metrics this gap between automated monitoring and manual auditing methods can be narrowed down significantly. Finally, while certain parts of requirements can be assessed automatically by using measurable metrics, it does not mean that assessing all requirements in compliance frameworks can be fully automated or that all results could be approved as such and thus a 100% automation coverage will not be feasible. As an example, automated natural language processing tools can be used to verify that certain processes are documented in policies, but the verification of these processes might require human interviews or manual process observations.

The initial certification audit of an organization will most likely require more work than before. The implementation of MEDINA has to be verified in addition to the initial certification audit conducted by the auditor. However, this pays off in the surveillance audit which in turn does not require as much work as before, assuming that the results gained through continuous auditing can be utilized.

MEDINA validation to trust the evidence

Auditors need verification to trust the evidence collected by MEDINA. To trust the evidence, the auditor must accept the use of MEDINA components and trust the results. Why could this be a challenge? There is always a trust component involved when an auditor is reviewing evidence from an information system – has it been tampered with, is the evidence representing a truthful image of the circumstances, etc.. As an added component to the audit process, in addition to validating the evidence in relation to the requirements, the auditor should also validate the implementation of the MEDINA framework in order to have assurance that the framework provides suitable evidence. At least the following items should be considered:

- MEDINA is implemented throughout the scope and all applicable assets are being audited.
- All applicable requirements are being audited in all applicable assets.
 - The selected metrics are correct, suitable and meet the intent of the requirements.
- The metrics are correct, and measurements show truthful results.
- The evidence is protected from tampering and any attempt to alter the data can be identified.
 - MEDINA explores the leveraging of Blockchain and other innovative solutions to ensure integrity and accountability. For further reading see MEDINA deliverable D4.3¹⁴
- The audit trail is long enough to validate events in a specified time frame, e.g., since the last audit.

Based on the analysis of a Proof-Of-Concept¹⁵ on the metrics and framework created in the MEDINA project, it is possible to implement continuous monitoring which fulfils the intent of the written requirements by using automated evidence collection and analysis. This provides high expectations for the future, and it is likely that we will see a change in how audits are conducted and how the certification is managed. However, the implementation of the metrics must be evaluated case-by-case as each environment and scope is different in each audit. Like in many cases, industry best practices and guidance of governing bodies will eventually steer the notion of continuous auditing towards a standardized way. New metrics and ways to implement metrics will need constant development to suit the needs of different emerging cloud technologies and innovative solutions to ensure that the MEDINA framework stays up-to-date.

From continuous auditing to continuous certification

The term continuous certification currently exists as a concept and is not widely adopted in certification schemes. Why so? Simply because it would require continuous auditing which itself is not a mature concept. Ideally, once the maturity of continuous auditing is high enough, it will lead to continuous certification where the status of the certificate is automatically monitored and updated based on the continuous assessment

results. The challenge in the leap from continuous auditing to continuous certification is the fact that scheme owners have a major role in defining the boundaries on how this will be done. MEDINA proposes tools for managing the certificate life cycle¹⁴, but the actual decision-making process is heavily dependent on EUCS and other certification schemes. There could be multiple implementation methods for continuous certification varying from auditee-implemented evidence storage solutions with auditor access to sophisticated auditor-implemented SOC-type (Security Operation Center) monitoring solutions. However, the approved solutions are to be chosen by the scheme owners and industries since continuous certification will change the whole ecosystem of how certificate registries work. There are still some challenges to be solved such as:

- What is the process for changing the status of certificates?
- How are findings categorized as major and minor non-conformities automatically?
- What are the different thresholds when multiple minor non-conformities start to affect certification?
 - What sort of timeline is acceptable for corrective actions before the auditor/automated system must react to the situation?
- What are the criteria for certificate suspension in a tool-assisted, automated decision making?
- Is the certificate suspended automatically after a major finding or after the auditor's analysis?
- How is the certificate status logged throughout the cycle?
 - Is only the current state of the certificate available for the public, or is a log of certificate statuses available?
 - What happens if a major nonconformity causes an incident which has long-term effects, e.g., a data loss prevention control fails and data is lost to an unauthorized party?
 - How is the certificate status updated because simply fixing the control does not revert the original data loss?

The optimal solution could be that all significant findings leading possibly to certificate suspension would be evaluated by the auditor during a grace period and the evidence of all non-conformities would be saved throughout the certification life-cycle. By this way the probability of false positive findings affecting certification is minimized. As a downside, frequent auditor involvement might cause extensive time periods of uncertain certificate status and added work if non-conformities are frequent. Risk management is a major component in continuous certification to assess findings and their effects on certification. For example, a failure in a security control in a low-priority

system versus a critical system would have a very different outcome. The failure is a nonconformity whatsoever, but the risk involved might be a deciding factor whether the nonconformity is a major or minor nonconformity. MEDINA includes a risk assessment component which can be utilized when assessing the risk associated to each asset and each finding.

Further considerations

This section discusses further considerations which could be potential targets for future research and most definitely will help the market adoption of continuous auditing and continuous certification.

Standardization & regulation

For MEDINA, and moreover in a larger context, continuous auditing and certification to become an industry best practice, it needs systematic standardization activities within the scope of MEDINA but most importantly by the information security certification industry, scheme owners and regulators. Certification schemes usually divide responsibilities and duties between different actors in order to avoid conflicts of interest. The parties owning and developing a certification scheme rarely do audits themselves but focus on maintaining the standard. Vice versa, this also means that auditors cannot start to offer continuous audit and certification services unless the standards, tools, market demand and standardized processes are in place. To make continuous audit and certification a norm and industry best practice, a joint effort consisting of standard development and standardization, regulation by authorities, market demand from cloud customers and strong CAB involvement is required.

Some of the CSPs will voluntarily start implementing continuous auditing such as MEDINA to gain a competitive advantage. They see the added value it creates in terms of business and in security. Unfortunately, all organizations will not be like that, and this emphasizes the need for regulation to encourage and enforce the change. Too heavy regulation will not be a feasible solution but mandatory continuous auditing in specified business sectors for certain critical environments could be an excellent starting point.

Trust through transparency

To gain the trust of cloud service providers, cloud customers and auditors, MEDINA needs to be transparent. A black box producing results without describing how results were achieved will not satisfy any auditor. Moreover, no organization will install a component to any business-critical environment if its trustworthiness from a security perspective and evidence trustworthiness perspective cannot be verified. When auditors have the possibility to understand and verify the trustworthiness of MEDINA components and the specific implementation in each auditee's environment, the results can be trusted. Trustworthiness is not only a concern for auditors but also for CSPs. There is no point in using a system if the trustworthiness cannot be verified. Considering that the tools aim to help understand the security status of an environment, false information is not beneficial to anyone.

Eventually, the solution could be that the MEDINA components are either provided as open-source and/or certified with a relevant certification, but currently there are no feasible product certification solutions. Additionally, certification of these tools does not guarantee reliable results since each installation is always depending on the environment and implementation where it is installed. While a certification would guarantee a certain security baseline, the implementation of the MEDINA tools in the target environment still has a significant impact on the results. The auditor must verify the trustworthiness of the configuration in each case separately and the level of detail this requires might vary. A widely adopted “industry accepted” tool might be rather simple to verify but a custom-made solution could require specialized skills to understand. Like in many cases, the acceptance criteria for the tools will likely develop as the tools become more common.

Conclusions

This paper has provided a brief introduction to MEDINA and its proposed solution to answer a challenge faced by many organizations from the perspective of a security auditor. By achieving continuous auditing, the cloud computing industry can significantly increase the level of trust in a single audit, but eventually in the certificate itself. For auditors MEDINA offers a fantastic opportunity to add another audit method to be used in an audit and further increase their trust in the audit results.

The involvement of the automation component in the audit will have changes in all levels of the audit process starting from the verification of the used tools to verifying pieces of evidence. One has to ensure that continuous auditing is implemented

correctly to have trust in the results. To achieve that, transparency of the framework, tools and customer implementation is a key factor. Additionally, adjusting the audit processes will need some time and guidance. However, when done correctly, continuous auditing allows much larger sample sizes from a much longer time period when time can be focused on finding non-conformities from results instead of manual assessments based on the auditor’s sample. Continuous certification is the next step from continuous auditing. In order for it to work and become an industry best practice, it requires continuous auditing to be a mature and widespread concept. In addition to that, scheme owners need to define the requirements and guidelines for automated certification life cycle management. MEDINA proposes solutions to all of these challenges, but the scheme owners are the authority to decide the proper approach.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

No data are associated with this article.

Acknowledgements

We appreciate the collaboration of MEDINA partners and the members of the ESG (Expert Stakeholders Group) for their contribution to the definition of the continuous auditing and certification process in MEDINA. This work has been partially funded by the European project MEDINA (Horizon 2020 Research and innovation Programme, under the grant agreement no 952633).

References

- Avram MG: **Advantages and challenges of adopting cloud computing from an enterprise perspective**. *Proc Technol*. 2014; **12**: 529–534. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kumar A: **Cloud Computing Challenges: A Survey**. *International Journal of Computer Science and Engineering Technology*. 2015; **6**: 602. [Reference Source](#)
- European Commission: **Cybersecurity act**. 2023. [Reference Source](#)
- ENISA: **European cybersecurity certification scheme for cloud services**. 2023. [Reference Source](#)
- MEDINA project: **MEDINA web site**. 2023. [Reference Source](#)
- Etzaniz I, Leskinen M, Regueiro C, et al.: **An architecture proposal for the MEDINA framework**. 2022. [Reference Source](#)
- Etzaniz I, Alonso J: **MEDINA D2.2 continuously certifiable technical and organizational measures and catalogue of cloud security metrics-v2**. January 2023. [Reference Source](#)
- Yautsiukhin A: **MEDINA D4.5 Methodology and tools for risk-based assessment and security control reconfiguration - v2**. April 2023. [Reference Source](#)
- Petrocchi M, Fazzolari M: **MEDINA D2.5 specification of the cloud security certification language - v3**. April 2023. [Reference Source](#)
- Ratkajec H: **MEDINA D3.6 tools and techniques for collecting evidence of technical and organisational measures - v3**. May 2023. [Reference Source](#)
- Opara S, Leskinen M: **MEDINA D7.3 Market, Innovation and Applicability Analysis**. December 2021. [Reference Source](#)
- ISO/IEC 17021-1: 2015(en). **Conformity assessment — Requirements for bodies providing audit and certification of management systems — Part 1: Requirements**. 2015. [Reference Source](#)
- Benedetto D, Caimi C, Ibrahim A, et al.: **D5.5 MEDINA integrated solution-v3**. August 2023. [Reference Source](#)
- Kunz I: **MEDINA D4.3 tools and techniques for the management and evaluation of cloud security certifications - v3**. April 2023. [Reference Source](#)
- Luna J, Ruebsamen T, Weiss P, et al.: **MEDINA: First impressions on experimenting with automated monitoring requirements of the upcoming eu cybersecurity certification scheme for cloud services**. 2021. [Reference Source](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 12 March 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18041.r36549>

© 2024 David Michels J. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

? **Johan David Michels**

Queen Mary University of London, London, England, UK

I commend the authors for writing a well-written, accessible open letter introducing the notion of continuous auditing and certification. The topic is of interest to those involved in the regulation of cybersecurity, including through certification schemes. The paper sets out clearly the differences between (1) point-in-time audits; (2) continuous auditing; and (3) continuous certification. Cloud computing, the EUCS, and MEDINA provide a helpful practical context to illustrate these points. I recommend the article for indexing, subject to the below revisions. (As a caveat, I add that my expertise is in cybersecurity regulation, not in computer science or security auditing, so I cannot comment on all the technical aspects of the analysis.)

First, in terms of style, there are a few minor language errors, which could be easily fixed in copy-editing (e.g. p. 3 "the its risk appetite" and "Digital evidence are", or p.5 "the opportunities [...] is" and "great opportunities both the auditee".)

Second, in terms of substance, my main concern is that the paper does not reflect on the possible downsides of a continuous auditing approach. As a result, it comes across as rather one-sided in favour of MEDINA. While continuous auditing has clear benefits over point-in-time audits, the paper could for instance consider whether automated monitoring of metrics can fully capture relevant vulnerabilities. It strikes me that some security measures (e.g. is software up to date; is the firewall configured correctly; is two-factor authentication set up where appropriate) can be better captured through such metrics than others (e.g. do accounts have role-appropriate privileges). For other measures, I'm just not sure (e.g. are any users using default or weak passwords, or re-using compromised passwords from private accounts; how susceptible are users to phishing attacks, etc.). It would be helpful if the paper discussed some of the weaknesses and identified the limits of this approach. A separate question is the extent to which such monitoring could apply to any underlying sub-processors in the cloud provider's supply chain.

In addition, I think it would be helpful if the paper mentioned a practical example of a metric that lends itself well to continuous auditing. For example, the paper could spell out a security objective; then state how that objective can be achieved through a certain security measure; and then

explain how the implementation of that measure can be measured by means of a metric that can be automatically monitored so that continuous auditing can provide a level of assurance. It need only be a single paragraph, but it might help readers who are not versed in security auditing (such as myself) to understand the concept better.

Finally, I offer an observation, without per se suggesting any revision. On p.7, the authors suggest risk management as a component in continuous certification, with the risk involved being a deciding factor whether a non-conformity is major or minor, which in turn helps determine consequences in terms of either (1) correcting the non-conformity during a grace period; or (2) suspending certificate status. I note that such a risk-based approach would be in line with the risk-based approach to incident notification under the GDPR Art. 33-34 and the NISD Art.16. Going further, one might consider continuous auditing to be part of a bigger, layered system of notifications under EU law, in which at the lowest level, a non-conformity is notified to an external auditor for analysis; which in case of a major non-conformity could lead to a CAB notification and possibly a certificate suspension; while a security incident (that is: an actual breach) must be notified to a regulator (under GDPR and/or NSID) for potential investigation and enforcement (including fines). Just a thought.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

No

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Yes

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Yes

Competing Interests: I am a member of the Cloud Legal Project at the Centre for Commercial Law Studies, Queen Mary University of London. I am grateful to Microsoft for the generous financial support that makes this research project possible. Responsibility for views expressed, however, remains solely with me. You can find out more about the project and its funding here: <https://www.qmul.ac.uk/cloudlegal/>.

Reviewer Expertise: Cybersecurity regulation; cloud computing law; data protection law;

commercial law studies

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 08 Apr 2024

Cristina Martinez

Dear Johan David, Thank you very much for reviewing our article and for your helpful comments. We have addressed them in version v2 of the article. You can see our responses below: First, in terms of style, there are a few minor language errors, which could be easily fixed in copy-editing (e.g. p. 3 "the its risk appetite" and "Digital evidence are", or p.5 "the opportunities [...] is" and "great opportunities both the auditee".) [MMC1]

Second, in terms of substance, my main concern is that the paper does not reflect on the possible downsides of a continuous auditing approach. As a result, it comes across as rather one-sided in favour of MEDINA. While continuous auditing has clear benefits over point-in-time audits, the paper could for instance consider whether automated monitoring of metrics can fully capture relevant vulnerabilities. It strikes me that some security measures (e.g. is software up to date; is the firewall configured correctly; is two-factor authentication set up where appropriate) can be better captured through such metrics than others (e.g. do accounts have role-appropriate privileges). For other measures, I'm just not sure (e.g. are any users using default or weak passwords, or re-using compromised passwords from private accounts; how susceptible are users to phishing attacks, etc.). It would be helpful if the paper discussed some of the weaknesses and identified the limits of this approach. [MMC2] A separate question is the extent to which such monitoring could apply to any underlying sub-processors in the cloud provider's supply chain [TS4]

In addition, I think it would be helpful if the paper mentioned a practical example of a metric that lends itself well to continuous auditing. For example, the paper could spell out a security objective; then state how that objective can be achieved through a certain security measure; and then explain how the implementation of that measure can be measured by means of a metric that can be automatically monitored so that continuous auditing can provide a level of assurance. It need only be a single paragraph, but it might help readers who are not versed in security auditing (such as myself) to understand the concept better. [MMC5]

Finally, I offer an observation, without per se suggesting any revision. On p.7, the authors suggest risk management as a component in continuous certification, with the risk involved being a deciding factor whether a non-conformity is major or minor, which in turn helps determine consequences in terms of either (1) correcting the non-conformity during a grace period; or (2) suspending certificate status. I note that such a risk-based approach would be in line with the risk-based approach to incident notification under the GDPR Art. 33-34 and the NISD Art.16. Going further, one might consider continuous auditing to be part of a bigger, layered system of notifications under EU law, in which at the lowest level, a non-conformity is notified to an external auditor for analysis; which in case of a major non-

conformity could lead to a CAB notification and possibly a certificate suspension; while a security incident (that is: an actual breach) must be notified to a regulator (under GDPR and/or NSID) for potential investigation and enforcement (including fines). Just a thought. [TS7]

[MMC1]Language errors have been corrected [MMC2]This suggestion has been addressed in the new section entitled "Challenges in continuous auditing and MEDINA" [TS4]Added a chapter called "**Challenges in continuous auditing and MEDINA**" [MMC5]An example has been introduced in the section entitled "MEDINA framework" [TS7]I agree with the reviewer, but this issue is something to be decided by the EU and scheme owners. I like the idea that the notification system would be built in to the system but it is out of the scope of this project.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 02 January 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18041.r36543>

© 2024 Santos H. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Henrique Santos

Department of Information Systems, Universidade do Minho, Braga, Braga, Portugal

The paper addresses a very pertinent question that may be of interest to the entire cybersecurity research community, particularly management and certification. It doesn't follow a scientific structure or a scientific method, but it illustrates a model that could be useful.

The use of bibliographical references does not follow a standard format, but this is an aspect that the editors could consider.

The authors can improve the paper with the following changes:

1. The title should explicitly mention the application context: Cloud Computing
2. Continuous monitoring and certification is not exactly a new topic. We would therefore expect some references to this subject and how it has been approached in other contexts.
3. One of the most complex problems in OT certification (continuous or otherwise) is the correct choice of metrics. The paper states that the metrics are derived from the security requirements/objectives defined in the EUCS, pointing to another project deliverable. However, a description, even if minimal, of how the metrics are identified would be desirable. They go on to say that they use a dedicated language to facilitate the automatic identification of metrics, but the way they do it could be clearer.
4. It is not expected that all security objectives, especially those of an organisational and operational nature, will benefit from a continuous certification scheme. It would be interesting to have a section reflecting on the impact of what can/should be continuously audited in a full cybersecurity audit programme (even if restricted to CSPs).

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Partly

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

No

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Yes

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Not applicable

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Cybersecurity; Computer Engineering; Information Systems

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 08 Apr 2024

Cristina Martinez

Dear Henrique, Thank you very much for reviewing our article and for your helpful comments. We have addressed them in version v2 of the article. You can see our responses below: [The use of bibliographical references does not follow a standard format, but this is an aspect that the editors could consider\[MMC1\]](#) . The authors can improve the paper with the following changes: 1. [The title should explicitly mention the application context: Cloud Computing.\[MMC2\]](#) 2. [Continuous monitoring and certification is not exactly a new topic. We would therefore expect some references to this subject and how it has been approached in other contexts.\[MMC3\]](#) 3. [One of the most complex problems in OT certification \(continuous or otherwise\) is the correct choice of metrics. The paper states that the metrics are derived from the security requirements/objectives defined in the EUCS, pointing to another project deliverable. However, a description, even if minimal, of how the metrics are identified would be desirable. They go on to say that they use a dedicated language to facilitate the automatic identification of metrics, but the way they do it could be](#)

clearer.[MMC4] 4. It is not expected that all security objectives, especially those of an organisational and operational nature, will benefit from a continuous certification scheme. It would be interesting to have a section reflecting on the impact of what can/should be continuously audited in a full cybersecurity audit programme (even if restricted to CSPs). [MMC5]

[MMC1]We have used the format of references defined in the ORE template for Overleaf (APA standard) [MMC2]The title has been changed as follows: "**Continuous Auditing and Continuous Certification of Cloud Services in MEDINA – Security Auditor’s View** "

[MMC3]We have elaborated on this suggestion at the end of the "Introduction" section. In addition, 3 references to papers have been added. [MMC4]A sentence about how metrics have been elicited has been included in the section "MEDINA framework" [MMC5]The "Introduction" section of the paper explains that the security objectives that can be continuously monitored are precisely identified in the EUCS, and belong to the high assurance level. The focus of MEDINA is on these high level requirements that are suitable for continuous automated monitoring. Organizational objectives can be also continuously monitored in MEDINA, but the periodicity defined for them is much higher than for operational controls. We have added a paragraph in section "MEDINA framework" to clarify it. Best regards, Cristina Martinez

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.